
FIELD CROP PRODUCTION TECHNOLOGY

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Annotation.

Agricultural crop production technology is a complex of agrotechnical measures that ensure high and high – quality tannery, environmentally friendly crop production, comply with the biological characteristics of crops, soil and climatic conditions. The implementation of these activities in the period when different forms of ownership are developing is very difficult.

Key words.

crop, production, planting, agricultural, varieties, hybrids, temperature, water, fertilizers.

Introduction

The purpose of plant science is the production of environmentally friendly, low cost, high –quality and abundant crops using the biological characteristics of crops, varieties, hybrids, a system of agrotechnical measures suitable for the soil – climatic conditions of the region. The tasks of cultivation technology, the growth and development of the plant in moderation, for the formation of high yields –the introduction of scientifically based crop rotation, placement of the crop after the best predecessor, the creation of an optimal water –air, nutrition regime for the good development of the root system in soil work, the effective use of organic –ore fertilizers, the use of integral (harmonized), Varieties that are included in the state register or are promising, are suitable for planting hybrids, harvesting in the short term, without loss, timely and high-quality execution of preliminary processing and storage measures. Agricultural crop production technology is a complex of agrotechnical measures that ensure high and high – quality tannery, environmentally friendly crop production, comply with the biological characteristics of crops, soil and climatic conditions. In crop production technology, the main and pre-sowing technological measures of soil processing, fertilizing, preparation of seeds for sowing, planting, crop care, harvesting are carried out in all crops. In the production of certain crops, there are features of their own cultivation, which include measures to inoculate the seeds of legumes, to water the stems of fiber crops.

The full use of the achievements of the development of scientific technology in agriculture, the biological potential of crops, varieties, hybrids, increasing crop yields, the amount of grown products as a result of managing the growth and development of plants is one of the main directions of field crop production technology. In cultivation technology, taking into account the biological characteristics of the crop, it is required to fully meet its needs, raise the culture of farming, increase the payment of tribute to the cocktail on the basis of the laws of the market economy. Currently, a wide variety of technologies are used, including biologizing agricultural crop production technology (Agrobiotechnology), anti-erosion technology, energy-saving technology, intensive technology and other types. In the technology of growing agricultural crops, technological maps of each crop are drawn up. The history of each field, agrochemical indicators, phytosanitary condition (weeds, diseases, pests), crop rotation, varieties are indicated, the passport of the field is drawn up. Changes in soil fertility, productivity are recorded in the field passport. The implementation of these activities in the period when different forms of ownership are developing is very difficult. The issues of substantiating crop planning using the achievements of Science and technology, increasing the coefficients of the use of headlights, water consumption, active or effective temperature, water, fertilizers are developed and improved taking into account soil -climatic conditions. Consistent, high-quality execution of agrotechnical measures, compliance with technological discipline ensure high and high-quality yields. In the application of Agrotechnology in the cultivation of field crops in Uzbekistan, the requirements for the development of crop rotation, soil -climatic conditions, demand for this crop product on the market, energy, resource-saving, environmentally friendly product are observed.

Placing crops after a good predecessor, preventing one crop from being planted in a single area for many years in a row is considered important agrotechnical measures. Neutralization of the soil environment. About half (50 %) of irrigated land in Uzbekistan is saline land. In such saline soils, over $R_h - 7$, the soil brine is washed, depending on the degree of salinity. The soil brine is washed once or several times in the autumn, winter seasons. Liming is carried out when the soil environment is sour (acidic). The bulk of field crops is good when the soil environment is neutral $RH -6 -7$ develops, grows. Working the soil. Basic soil work, work before planting and during the growing season events are held.

Planting. When preparing seeds for sowing, seeds of fertile, resistant to diseases, pests and unfavorable factors of external, varieties included in the state

register are selected. The seeds are cleaned, sorted out before planting, the phytosanitary condition is improved and brought to a state that meets the requirements of the state template. In Uzbek conditions, crops can be planted in Spring, Summer, Autumn, Winter. Sowing dates will depend on the type of crop, variety, purpose of planting and biology. Depending on the biological characteristics of the species, variety, hybrid, the optimal planting dates for a fertile soil -climatic region are determined. The seeds of long-day, cereal crops begin to sprout at a temperature of 1 -20 C, the grass withstands frosts of 3 -80 C. These plants can be planted in early spring.

The plants of the short day are heat-loving, the seeds germinate 8 -120s, the grass -10s die in the cold. When planting these crops, the soil temperature is taken into account as well as calendar periods. The sowing dates in determined depending on the moisture in the soil, the onset of precipitation. The method of planting, the norm will depend on the type of product obtained from the crop. One crop itself is planted in different sizes, thicknesses, depending on whether the grain is planted for seed or blue mass. Sowing dates can vary depending on the mechanical composition of the soil, the depth of placement of waters. The mechanical composition is light, sandy soils quickly warm up, Clay soils, on the contrary, warm up slowly, soils located far from waters are rapidly matured, soils located close by are late maturing. Accordingly, even in one farm, crops can be planted for different periods, taking into account field. Crops can be planted in wide rows, in narrow rows, in rows, in a row, in a ribbon method, by adding. Planting methods are determined taking into account the type, variety, biological characteristics of the crop, the purpose of planting, weed contamination of the field. Planting standards are estimated to be in the range of the seed is given in terms of hectares or kg, s, t hectares, and the weight of 1000 seeds is taken into account.

The planting depth will depend on the large size of the seed, soil moisture, mechanical composition, removal of the seedpalla to the soil surface and varies from 1 -2 to 6 -12 CM. Crop Care. Technological activities such as loosening rows, loss of resin, feeding with mineral and organic fertilizers, weed control, diseases, pest control, retardants, the use of biologically active substances are included in Crop Care. Crop Care is carried out depending on the biological characteristics of the crop, variety, hybrid, the type of product to be obtained. Harvest periods, methods are carried out depending on the state of the crop, the technological system used. In this case, defoliation design, senication measures can be carried out.

The main problems in the cultivation of agricultural crops and their directions. High use of chemical means, mechanization, meliorization in the cultivation of agricultural crops during the science and technology revolution, causes pollution of the biosphere, soil salinity, the development of erosion processes, costs in the cultivation of a certain amount (s, t) of products, an increase in the cost of means of Labor, a shortage of water and energy resources. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, in combination with obtaining a rich and high-quality crop in the cultivation of agricultural crops, increase soil fertility, optimize the use of chemicals, save water, introduce new methods of irrigation (raining, drip, subsoil) into production, introduce into practice varieties resistant to drought, salt, diseases, pests, other unfavorable factors of nature, it will be necessary to solve the problems of increasing the effectiveness of the use of organic and ore fertilizers. The problem of energy in the cultivation of field crop products is becoming more urgent. The consumption of energy resources in mechanization, irrigation, fertilizer application, pesticide application is sharply increasing. Currently, the energy in the form of a product is 2 -5 times more compared to the energy spent in the cultivation of herbal products. But to get an extra harvest, you will have to spend more energy. Developed countries increased the yield of agricultural crops in the United States and Japan by 1.2 -1.5 times in the following years, when per hectare was traveled, energy consumption increased by 3.5 -5.1 times.

Conclusion

Doubling the yield of agricultural crops requires the expenditure of a large amount of energy on the technologies currently being used. Modern agrotechnologies are based on the use of natural fuel. And the reserves of natural fuels are very limited. In the 21st century in particular, there is a growing shortage of fossil fuels in crop production. An increase in the cost of energy sources leads to an increase in the cost of plant products and can prevent agriculture from developing in an accelerated way. Intensive grain crop rotation, introduction of large amounts of nitrogen fertilizers into the soil, immunity to fertile but diseases leads to an increase in the degree of harm to diseases (especially fungi) of the prevalence of varieties of low-grain crops. While pesticides are widely used in some developed countries, disease and pest damage are increasing. The prevalence of co-productive varieties of the same type of origin maintains the risk of rapid morbidity due to the uniformity of murtak plasma in them.

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